

D 3.3 – Report on family of WBG-based integrated traction inverters with dynamically reconfigurable windings and innovative cooling solutions

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
2L-VSI	Two-level voltage source inverter
AFPMSM	Axial-flux permanent magnet synchronous machine
Back-EMF	Back electromotive force
CCM	Continuous conduction mode
EMC	Electromagnetic compatibility
IOC	Integrated on-board charger

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PFC	Power factor corrector
PMSM	Permanent magnet synchronous machine

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1 Publishable Executive Summary

This report, part of the Horizon Europe-funded HighScope project, presents a comprehensive study on innovative traction inverter systems for electric vehicles (EVs) based on wide bandgap (WBG) semiconductors. The focus is on dynamically reconfigurable windings and integrated on-board charging (IOC) solutions, aiming to enhance efficiency, scalability, power density, and cost-effectiveness in next-generation EV drivetrain architectures.

The core innovation centers around e-gears, which are reconfigurable winding systems that extend the operating range of electric traction machines by dynamically altering the winding topology between series and parallel configurations. Two main implementations are explored: one using mechanical relays and the other based on semiconductor tap-changer circuits.

The mechanical relay-based e-gear offers a cost-effective and efficient solution, enabling a switch between high-torque (series) and high-speed (parallel) modes. An extension of the speed range from 1000 to 2000 rpm with minimal efficiency loss (only 0.09% reduction compared to baseline), and a reconfiguration time under 35 ms, comparable to high-end automotive gearboxes were achieved.

The semiconductor-based e-gear employs a more sophisticated architecture using SiC MOSFETs and diode rectifiers. It enables faster switching (<10 ms) and avoids torque interruption during transitions. However, this comes at the cost of increased complexity and reduced efficiency (average drop of 3.46%) due to additional conduction and switching losses.

Additionally, the report investigates both single-phase and three-phase integrated on-board chargers, leveraging the same motor windings to provide bidirectional charging functionality. Multiple configurations are analyzed, including boost PFC, interleaved PFC, and hybrid topologies. The designs aim to reduce component count, improve power factor, and eliminate the need for access to the motor's star point, making them viable for single-motor EV platforms.

Simulation and experimental results confirm the feasibility of the proposed designs, highlighting the trade-offs between system complexity, efficiency, torque capability, and reconfiguration speed. Overall, the HighScope e-gear and IOC technologies provide a promising pathway for more compact, versatile, and efficient EV drivetrain systems.

2 Introduction

In an e-gear system, motor windings are reconfigured based on the operating point of the vehicle. This reconfiguration requires both adapted motor windings and dedicated reconfiguration switches. Two primary classifications of switches are explored: mechanical relays in Section 3 and semiconductors in Section 4. Each topology presents unique advantages and disadvantages.

An e-gear system utilizing mechanical relays offers a straightforward and cost-effective implementation, higher efficiency, and a wide operating range. However, its main drawbacks are an instantaneous torque dip during reconfiguration and mechanical wear of the relay contacts. Semiconductor-based e-gear systems eliminate the torque interruption and wear issues but involve more complex and expensive

components. Additionally, certain reconfigurations in semiconductor-based systems lead to partial motor utilization, resulting in lower efficiency. The inclusion of snubber circuits to manage reconfiguration transients can also negatively impact efficiency.

Despite these considerations, the limited lifespan of a vehicle makes the wear of mechanical relays less of a concern. Furthermore, the torque drop during reconfiguration is relatively minor compared to existing automatic mechanical gearboxes. Consequently, mechanical relays are chosen as the optimal solution to realize an e-gear for electric vehicles.

The second part of this report focuses on repurposing the e-gear's reconfiguration switches to facilitate AC integrated on-board charging (single-phase or three-phase) by reusing the inverter switches and motor windings. A crucial constraint here is to prevent torque generation during charging. For single-phase charging, four strategies are proposed, all of which utilize both the traction inverter power electronic switches and the motor windings. For three-phase charging, one solution is thoroughly developed, emphasizing the reuse of reconfiguration switches and the prevention of torque production during charging.

Both aspects, i.e. reconfiguration for e-gear and charging, are initially studied through simulation. The concepts are explained and proper models are introduced where necessary. This phase involves introducing appropriate control strategies and tuning their parameters to achieve desired performance. Subsequently, measurements are conducted on a test setup for both reconfiguration for e-gear and charging and compared with the simulation results. The control strategies, while previously covered in the control deliverable, are reiterated here for completeness.

The results obtained demonstrate that reconfiguring the motor windings with the reconfiguration switches can effectively implement both an e-gear and an integrated on-board charger, achieving the desired performance.

3 E-Gear with Mechanical Relays

3.1 Architecture and General Working Principle

The e-gear depicted in Figure 1 makes use of mechanical relays to change from a series to a parallel connection and vice versa. A standard three-phase drive is extended with three single pole single throw power relays and three single pole double throw power relays for this purpose. High torque levels can be achieved with the series connection, while the parallel connection allows to extend the speed range. When the phase windings (A , B and C) are divided into two equal parts (A_1 and A_2 , B_1 and B_2 , and C_1 and C_2), the operating ranges of the two configurations are depicted in Figure 2.

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Figure 1: Series/parallel reconfiguration by means of three single pole single throw power relays, and three single pole double throw power relays: (a) series connection for high torque, (b) parallel connection for high speed.

Figure 2: Operating ranges of the e-gear: (dashed red) e-gear in series connection, (dashed blue) e-gear in parallel connection.

The e-gear can be retrofitted on a standard permanent magnet synchronous machine (PMSM) with a standard three-phase drive. The only requirements for the PMSM are that it has two paths per phase with identical back electromotive force (back-EMF), and that it has open-end windings. If the back-EMF of the parallel paths is not identical in amplitude or in phase, circulating currents occur in the parallel mode, which deteriorate the efficiency, or even exceed the current limits of the PMSM. The series/parallel reconfiguration can be applied to both concentrated and distributed winding configurations.

Depending on the initial motor design, the required parallel paths can be automatically present in the PMSM. A PMSM with 48 stator slots and 4 pole pairs, for instance, inherently has four parallel paths with identical back-EMF per phase. Another option to create the parallel paths is the use of a bifilar winding,

as shown in Figure 3. In this case, two parallel strands are wound together at the same time, making two contiguous windings. This last technique can be applied to any motor, regardless of its number of stator slots or stator teeth, and its number of pole pairs.

Figure 3: Stator tooth with bifilar winding (from CliMAFlux)

3.2 (Dis)Advantages of Mechanical Relays

Mechanical switches can realise changes in winding connection in a simple and inexpensive way, as they can conduct AC currents. Furthermore, they have low conduction losses. On the other hand, mechanical switches exhibit transition times in the order of tens to hundreds of milliseconds due to mechanical constraints, and they are prone to wear [1]. However, even the most advanced mechanical gearboxes in cars exhibit shift times in the same order of magnitude [2]. Furthermore, as the mechanical lifetime of mechanical relays is expected to be at least one million operations [3], also the lifetime of the relays is not a real restriction for electric passenger vehicles, which are only designed for less than 500,000 km themselves [4].

3.3 Experimental Test Setup

The prototype, the e-gear implementation, and the test setup are part of the CliMAFlux project, as described in the deviations section. For a detailed description, we therefore refer to *D3.2: Integration strategy (adopted from EU HighScope) for PE into axial machines* of the CliMAFlux project.

3.4 Static Behaviour and Operating Range

Switching from the series to the parallel configuration halves the back-EMF of the PMSM, and hence allows for a doubling of the speed range for the same DC-bus voltage. The relation between the torque ranges of the two configurations, however, depends on the inverter's current rating and/or the PMSM's current rating. When the inverter is rated for the series connection (i.e., when the inverter's current rating equals the PMSM's current rating), the parallel configuration can only produce half the torque level of the series connection. This is due to the fact that the inverter current has to split over the two parallel branches. However, when the inverter is rated for the parallel connection, both configurations can achieve the same torque level.

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To assess the static behaviour and the operating range of the series and the parallel configuration on the test setup, the mechanical relays are continuously steered to establish respectively a series or a parallel connection. The AFPMSM and its three-phase inverter are controlled by means of a standard three-phase field-oriented vector current controller, with anti-reset windup and feedforward to decouple the d - and the q -axis. Each configuration has its own set of control parameters. For the test setup of Figure 5, it is chosen to use the PI parameters $K_p = 11.6$ and $K_i = 4000$ for both configurations and for both the d - and q -axis. The feedforward terms, however, are different for each configuration. The required machine parameters are listed in Table 1. The switching frequency is equal to 5 kHz, while the sampling frequency and the controller's update frequency amount to 5 kHz.

The efficiency map of the complete drive (i.e., AFPMSM, inverter, and reconfiguration switches) is shown in Figure 4 for the series connection, together with the machine losses and the inverter losses. The measurements are performed at mechanical speeds $N = \{200, 400, \dots, 1000\}$ r/min and q -current set-points $I_q^* = \{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$ A. A similar graph is shown in Figure 5 for the parallel connection, with measuring points $N = \{200, 400, \dots, 2000\}$ r/min, and $I_q^* = \{1, 2, \dots, 9\}$ A.

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Figure 4: Experimentally obtained efficiency, machine losses and inverter losses for the series configuration.

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Figure 5: Experimentally obtained efficiency, machine losses and inverter losses for the parallel configuration.

It can indeed be concluded that switching from a series to a parallel connection allows to double the speed range, i.e. from 1000 to 2000 r/min for the same DC-bus voltage $V_{DC} = 400$ V. For the series connection, the torque range is limited to 12.3 N·m due to the PMSM's current limit of 5 A. In the parallel connection, it is the inverter's current rating of 9 A that limits the current through the PMSM to 4.5 A, and the torque to 11 N·m. The parallel configuration suffers from higher inverter losses than the series configuration for the same torque/speed operating points. This is due to the fact that the inverter has to deliver twice the current to the parallel configuration compared to the series configuration in order to obtain the same

torque level. The measured machine losses are similar for both configurations. In theory, the machine losses should be slightly higher for the parallel configuration, since its lower stator inductance introduces more current ripple. However, the mechanical power measurement (based on the sensor inputs of the incremental encoder and the torque transducer) is not accurate enough to observe this phenomenon at all common operating points. The effect on the efficiency of the addition of the six mechanical relays to the original drive is also limited: for the same operating range (i.e., for a torque $T_{em} \in [2 \quad 12]$ N·m and a speed $N \in [200 \quad 1000]$ r/min), the original drive (without reconfiguration unit) exhibits a measured average efficiency of 84.93%, whereas the average efficiency of the e-gear is measured to be 84.84%. This corresponds to an average loss of 7.15 W in the reconfiguration unit.

The joint operating range and efficiency map is shown in Figure 6. It confirms that the series/parallel reconfiguration can extend the efficient operating range of a PMSM. For low speeds, the series configuration is used. For high speeds, the parallel configuration is used.

Figure 6: Experimentally obtained efficiency map for the extended operating range. For mechanical speeds lower than 1000 r/min, the series configuration is used. For speeds above 1000 r/min, the parallel configuration is used.

3.5 Reconfiguration Strategy

3.5.1 Switching Procedure

To switch from one configuration to the other, the following procedure is followed:

1. Open all the switches of the 2L-VSI, in order to block the current in the PMSM and the relays during the reconfiguration. The wear of the mechanical relays is limited in this way. Start resetting the PI controller, and load the new control parameters.
2. Wait until the currents running through the PMSM and the relays have died out through the anti-parallel diodes.
3. Initiate the actual reconfiguration by sending the appropriate steering signals to the mechanical relays.
4. Wait until the contacts of the relays are opened or closed again, and the bouncing has stopped.
5. Stop resetting the PI controller. Resume normal operation with the new control parameters.

3.5.2 Simulation Results (using CliMAFlux adapted model for axial-flux actuator)

To simulate the transient response of the PMSM during reconfiguration, the PMSM is modelled as a six-phase machine in the abc-reference frame, with windings A_1, B_1, C_1, A_2, B_2 and C_2 as shown in Figure 1:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{L} \frac{d\mathbf{i}}{dt} + \mathbf{e},$$

with $\mathbf{x} = [x_{a,1} \ x_{b,1} \ x_{c,1} \ x_{a,2} \ x_{b,2} \ x_{c,2}]^T$ ($\mathbf{x} \in \{\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{i}, \mathbf{e}\}$), $\mathbf{R} = \text{diag}[R_s, \dots, R_s]$, and

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} L_m & M_1 & M_1 & M_2 & M_3 & M_3 \\ M_1 & L_m & M_1 & M_3 & M_2 & M_3 \\ M_1 & M_1 & L_m & M_3 & M_3 & M_2 \\ M_2 & M_3 & M_3 & L_m & M_1 & M_1 \\ M_3 & M_2 & M_3 & M_1 & L_m & M_1 \\ M_3 & M_3 & M_2 & M_1 & M_1 & L_m \end{bmatrix}.$$

\mathbf{v} represents the stator voltages (V), \mathbf{R} is the stator resistance matrix (Ω), \mathbf{i} represents the stator currents (A), \mathbf{L} is the inductance matrix (H), and \mathbf{e} contains the back-EMF caused by the permanent magnets (V). The machine parameters are listed in Table 1.

Figure 7 shows simulation results for different speed and torque levels. The simulation starts in the series connection, after which the winding connection of the AFPMSM is reconfigured at $t \in \{6, 18, 22, 28\}$ s. It can be noticed that the torque level is twice as high for the series connection as for the parallel connection under the same current set-point I_q^* . Under the parallel configuration, the speed can be raised above 1000 r/min, while this is not possible under the series configuration.

Figure 7: Simulation results for the e-gear with mechanical relays at different configurations, speeds and torque levels.

A detail of the simulated switching transient from parallel to series configuration is presented in Figure 8 for the operating point $I_q^* = 5$ A and $N = 700$ r/min. The five reconfiguration steps described in Section 3.5.1 are indicated on the graph. For $t < 19.6$ ms, the stator windings are connected in the parallel configuration, with the mechanical relays in the positions indicated in Figure 1(b). This means that the 3-phase current i_{abc} has an amplitude of 5 A, while the current amplitude of $i_{abc,1}$ and $i_{abc,2}$ through the parallel branches equals 2.5 A. The three 3-phase current sets are in phase with each other. At $t = 19.6$ ms, the current through the PMSM and the relays is interrupted by opening all the switches of the 2L-VSI. Only four switching periods later (at $t = 20$ ms), when the currents have died out, the relays are switched from their positions in Figure 1(b) to their positions in Figure 1(a). For the Potter & Brumfield T9GS5L14-5 mechanical relays used in this work, the maximum operate or release time including bounce equals 22 ms. The normal operation of the drive in series connection is hence resumed at $t = 42$ ms, with the control

parameters for the series connection. After the control transients have died out, a current with an amplitude of 5 A runs through all the windings of the PMSM. The zero-current interval of 22 ms causes a short torque interruption, which can be noticed in Figure 7. However, the switching transients take less than 35 ms, making the e-gear competitive with the gearbox of a Lamborghini Aventador, which has a reported shift time of 50 ms [2].

Figure 8: Simulated detail of the reconfiguration from parallel to series connection ($I_q^* = 5 \text{ A}$, $N = 700 \text{ r/min}$). The five steps of the switching procedure described in Section 3.5.1 are indicated.

Figure 9 shows a zoomed-in view of the simulated reconfiguration from a series to a parallel connection. The current is interrupted at $t = 79.6 \text{ ms}$, after which the switching of the mechanical relays is started at $t = 80 \text{ ms}$. The operation of the PMSM in parallel connection is resumed 22 ms later.

Figure 9: Simulated detail of the reconfiguration from series to parallel connection ($I_q^* = 5 \text{ A}$, $N = 700 \text{ r/min}$). The five steps of the switching procedure described in Section 3.5.1 are indicated.

3.5.3 Experimental Validation

Experimental results obtained with the test setup of Figure 5 are shown in Figure 10 for different speeds and torque levels. As in the simulation of Figure 7, the experiment starts in the series connection, after which the winding connection of the AFPMSM is reconfigured at $t \in \{6, 18, 22, 28\} \text{ s}$. Apart from the measurement noise on the torque signal, and the fact that the load motor is not able to keep the speed perfectly constant under a torque variation, the experimental results of Figure 10 are in good agreement with the simulation results of Figure 7. In the parallel configuration, the speed can indeed be raised above 1000 r/min. For the same q -current set-point I_q^* , the torque level is indeed twice as high for the series configuration as for the parallel configuration. Short torque interruptions occur during the reconfiguration.

Figure 10: Experimental results for the e-gear with mechanical relays at different configurations, speeds and torque levels.

Details of the reconfiguration transients are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12 for the same operating conditions as in simulation (i.e., $I_q^* = 5$ A and $N = 700$ r/min). The experiments are in good agreement with the simulation results of Figure 8 and Figure 9. They both confirm that the reconfiguration transients fade away in less than 35 ms. The e-gear thus indeed outperforms the shift time of the gearbox of a Lamborghini Aventador.

Figure 11: Measured detail of the reconfiguration from parallel to series connection ($I_q^* = 5 \text{ A}$, $N = 700 \text{ r/min}$). The five steps of the switching procedure described in Section 3.5.1 are indicated.

Figure 12: Measured detail of the reconfiguration from series to parallel connection ($I_q^* = 5 \text{ A}$, $N = 700 \text{ r/min}$). The five steps of the switching procedure described in Section 3.5.1 are indicated.

3.6 Conclusion

The e-gear with mechanical relays allows to change the winding connections of a PMSM from a series connection to a parallel connection and vice versa, while the machine is running. The series connection makes it possible to achieve the maximum torque level, while the parallel connection doubles the efficient speed range of the drive. The e-gear can be established by retrofitting a standard three-phase PMSM fed by a standard three-phase 2L-VSI with a switching unit comprising six inexpensive mechanical relays. The only requirements for the PMSM are that it has open-end windings, and that it has two paths per phase with identical back-EMF. These parallel paths can be created by means of a bifilar winding. During the reconfiguration, the current through the machine and the relays is blocked, in order to limit the wear of the mechanical relays, and hence to extend their lifetime. Both simulations and measurements on a 4 kW test setup validated the reconfiguration strategy. They confirm that the switching unit has almost no impact on the efficiency of the drive, and that all the reconfiguration transients have died out after less

than 35 ms. The shift time of the e-gear is hence competitive with the shift time of the most advanced mechanical gearboxes in cars.

4 E-Gear with Semiconductors

4.1 Architecture and General Working Principle

The e-gear depicted in Figure 13 makes use of a tap-changer circuit made of semiconductor components and a snubber circuit, which allows to shift the neutral point of the windings [1] [5] [6]. By shifting the neutral point of the windings with the tap-changer circuit, it is possible to feed only part of the wye connected phase winding. In this way, the number of stator turns – and hence the back-EMF – is reduced, which enables an extension of the speed range of the PMSM. However, a main disadvantage of this tap-changing technique is the low utilisation rate of the motor windings, as only part of the motor windings is used in high-speed mode.

Figure 13: Tap-changer circuit with (1) two switching cells, (2) a snubber circuit, and (3) two precharge resistors.

The e-gear can be retrofitted on a standard PMSM with a standard three-phase drive. The only requirement for the PMSM is that it needs to have open-end windings. The tap-changer circuit consists of two switching cells, a snubber circuit and two precharge resistors. Each switching cell comprises a three-phase full bridge diode rectifier that allows to open or close a current path for a three-phase AC current with only one unidirectional switch. Each switching cell is connected to a snubber circuit by means of two diodes. The goal of the snubber circuit is to absorb the surge energy and to eliminate voltage transients across the switches. The precharge resistors are required to limit the initial charging current into the snubber circuit.

By steering the two semiconductor switches of the tap-changer circuit – which are indicated as Q1 and Q2 in Figure 14 – two configurations can be established. When Q1 is open and Q2 is closed (as shown in Figure 14(a)), the inverter feeds all the stator turns of the PMSM. This means that high torque can be achieved in this configuration, because all the windings conduct current. However, this also means that the back-EMF, and hence the speed, is limited in this configuration. This high torque/low speed

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configuration is denoted as '5w' throughout this document. When Q2 is open and Q1 is closed (as illustrated in Figure 14(b)), only part of the stator turns per phase is fed. This means that higher speeds can be achieved, but less torque. This low torque/high speed configuration is denoted as '3w'. The switches Q1 and Q2 are always steered in a complementary way, and a small dead time is required between opening one switch and closing the other one, in order to avoid that the machine windings are short-circuited.

Figure 14: The tap-changer circuit allows to shift the neutral point of the windings: (a) all windings connected in series for high torque (open Q1, closed Q2) (5w), (b) only part of the windings connected in series for high speed (closed Q1, open Q2) (3w).

The potential extension of the operating range depends on the position of the tap-changer circuit. For the e-gear depicted in Figure 13 and Figure 14, for instance, one phase consists of five stator coils connected in series. The tap-changer circuit allows to reconfigure to a series connection of three stator coils per phase. The resulting operating range is depicted in Figure 15: the speed can be increased with a factor 5/3. In general, when the tap-changer circuit allows to reduce the number of stator turns from n_{tot} to n_{tc} , the speed can be extended with a factor n_{tot}/n_{tc} .

Figure 15: Operating range of the semiconductor-based e-gear: (dashed red) e-gear with five windings connected in series per phase, (dashed blue): e-gear with three windings connected in series per phase.

4.2 (Dis)Advantages of Semiconductor-Based Switches

The use of semiconductor-based switches has the advantage that the transition time to switch from one configuration to the other is very short (in the order of a few microseconds), and that the predicted lifetime of semiconductor-based switches in an electrical vehicle amounts to at least a couple of years under the New York city cycle (NYCC) [7]. However, compared to the mechanical relays, the reconfiguration unit is more complex: the semiconductor-based reconfiguration unit requires a three-phase full bridge diode rectifier to switch an AC current with only one uni-directional active switch. Furthermore, the three-phase full bridge diode rectifiers and the semiconductor-based switches Q1 and Q2 exhibit non negligible conduction losses. Also the snubber circuit generates additional losses.

4.3 Experimental Test Setup

The prototype, the e-gear implementation, and the test setup are part of the CliMAFlux project, as described in the deviations section. For a detailed description, we therefore refer to *D3.2: Integration strategy (adopted from EU HighScope) for PE into axial machines* of the CliMAFlux project.

4.4 Static Behaviour and Operating Range

Shifting the location of the neutral point with the tap-changer circuit illustrated in Figure 14 from the '5w' configuration to the '3w' configuration reduces the back-EMF of the PMSM with a factor $3/5$, and hence allows for an extension of the speed range with a factor $5/3$ for the same DC-bus voltage. On the other hand, the same stator current causes in the '3w' configuration only $3/5$ of the torque that it would generate in the '5w' configuration.

To assess the static behaviour and the operating range of the e-gear on the test setup, the tap-changer circuit is continuously steered to establish respectively the '5w' configuration of Figure 14(a) or the '3w' configuration of Figure 14(b). The AFPMSM and its three-phase inverter are controlled by means of a standard three-phase field-oriented vector current controller, with anti-reset windup and feedforward to

decouple the d - and q -axis. Each configuration has its own set of control parameters. For the ‘5w’ configuration, the PI parameters are tuned to $K_p = 2.9$ and $K_i = 1000$ for both the d - and q -axis. For the ‘3w’ configuration, the PI parameters are tuned to $K_p = 2.5$ and $K_i = 400$ for both the d - and q -axis. The machine parameters for the feedforward terms are listed in Table 2 for both configurations. The switching frequency is equal to 5 kHz, while the sampling frequency and the controller’s update frequency amount to 5 kHz.

The efficiency map of the complete drive (i.e., AFPMSM, inverter, and tap-changer circuit) is shown in Figure 16 for the ‘5w’ configuration of Figure 14(a). The measurements are performed at mechanical speeds $N = \{200, 400, \dots, 1000\}$ r/min and q -current set-points $I_q^* = \{2, 4, \dots, 10\}$ A. A similar graph is shown in Figure 17 for the ‘3w’ configuration of Figure 14(b), with measuring points $N = \{200, 400, \dots, 1400\}$ r/min and $I_q^* = \{2, 4, \dots, 10\}$ A.

Figure 16: Experimentally obtained efficiency for the ‘5w’ configuration of Figure 14(a).

Figure 17: Experimentally obtained efficiency for the ‘3w’ configuration of Figure 14(b).

It can indeed be concluded that shifting the neutral point allows to extend the speed range for the same DC-bus voltage $V_{DC} = 200$ V. In theory, it should be possible to extend the speed range from 1000 rpm to 1600 rpm. However, due to EMC issues, the maximum speed that could be tested was 1400 rpm. For the operating points that are achievable with both configurations, it is always better to use all the windings

of the machine: the same torque level can be achieved with lower currents and hence lower copper losses, and thus better efficiency in that case.

The addition of the tap-changer circuit has a negative impact on the efficiency, due to the conduction losses in the diode rectifiers and the semiconductor-based switches, but also due to the losses in the snubber circuit. For the same operating range (i.e., for a torque $T_{em} \in [2 \ 12]$ N·m and a speed $N \in [200 \ 1000]$ r/min, the original drive (without tap-changer circuit) exhibits a measured average efficiency of 84.93%, whereas the average efficiency of the e-gear wit tap-changer circuit is measured to be 81.47% on average.

The joint operating range and efficiency map is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Experimentally obtained efficiency map for the extended operating range. For mechanical speeds lower than 1000 r/min, all the stator turns are fed (i.e., ‘5w’ configuration). For speeds above 1000 r/min, only part of the stator turns is used (i.e., ‘3w’ configuration).

4.5 Reconfiguration Strategy

4.5.1 Switching Procedure

To switch from the configuration in which switch Q_x is closed and switch Q_y is open ($x, y \in \{1, 2\}, x \neq y$) to the configuration in which Q_x is open and Q_y is closed, the following procedure is followed:

1. Open switch Q_x . Start resetting the PI controllers, and load the new control parameters.
2. Wait for a period equal to the dead time of the semiconductor-based switches in order to avoid short-circuiting of the machine windings.
3. Stop resetting the PI controllers. Close switch Q_y . Resume normal operation with the new control parameters.

4.5.2 Experimental Results

Figure 19 shows experimental results for different speeds and torque levels. The experiment starts in the ‘5w’ configuration, after which the neutral point of the AFPMSM is shifted at $t \in \{6, 18, 22, 28\}$ s. It can be noticed that the torque level is a factor 5/3 higher for the ‘5w’ configuration than for the ‘3w’ configuration under the same current set-point I_q^* . Under the ‘3w’ configuration, the speed can be raised

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above 1000 r/min, while this is not possible under the ‘5w’ configuration. Since the dead time for switching amounts to only 1.3 μs , there is no torque interruption during the reconfiguration.

Figure 19: Experimental results for the semiconductor-based e-gear at different configurations, speeds and torque levels.

Figure 20 and Figure 21 show a zoomed-in view of the transients after the switching instants at respectively $t = 20$ s and $t = 80$ s for the operating point $I_q^* = 7$ A and $N = 700$ r/min. Due to the fact that the sampling period $T_{\text{sample}} = 200$ μs is larger than the dead time during which both Q1 and Q2 are open ($T_{\text{dead time}} = 1.3$ μs), the phase currents are distorted right after the switching instant, but not interrupted. The transients have died out after 10 ms. The reconfiguration with the semiconductor-based e-gear is indeed faster than the reconfiguration with the relays-based e-gear. The semiconductor-based e-gear hence also outperforms the shift time of the gearbox of a Lamborghini Aventador.

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Figure 20: Measured detail of the reconfiguration from '5w' to '3w' configuration ($I_q^* = 7 \text{ A}$, $N = 700 \text{ r/min}$).

Figure 21: Measured detail of the reconfiguration from '3w' to '5w' configuration ($I_q^* = 7 \text{ A}$, $N = 700 \text{ r/min}$).

4.6 Conclusion

The e-gear with the semiconductor-based tap-changer circuit allows to shift the neutral point of the PMSM, while the machine is running. The configuration in which all the windings are fed by means of the inverter makes it possible to achieve the maximum torque level, while reducing the number of stator turns fed by the inverter by means of a neutral point shift extends the speed range of the drive. The e-gear can be established by retrofitting a standard three-phase PMSM fed by a standard three-phase 2L-VSI with a switching unit comprising two unidirectional power semiconductor switches, two three-phase full bridge diode rectifiers, a snubber circuit, four diodes and two precharge resistors. The only requirement for the

PMSM is that it has open-end windings. Measurements on a 4 kW test setup validated the reconfiguration strategy. They confirm that the reconfiguration transients have died out after 10 ms, and that the torque is never interrupted. The shift time of the e-gear is hence competitive with the shift time of the most advanced mechanical gearboxes in cars. However, the addition of the tap-changer circuit negatively impacts the efficiency of the drive (-3.46%), due to conduction losses in the semiconductor power switches and the diodes, and losses in the snubber circuit.

5 Single-Phase integrated On-board charger

5.1 Motor windings configurations

Unlike conventional EV charger, motor windings should be studied for designing IOCs. Several winding configurations have been proposed in the literature to achieve torque cancellation in single-phase IOCs. These configurations vary in terms of the count of active switches in the AC-DC converter, the number of motors employed, and the number of reconfiguration switches utilized. Among these configurations, methods that require the fewest reconfiguration switches and only a single three-leg AC-DC converter feasible for implementation in one-motor powertrains are considered more promising and are discussed in this report. Figure 22 illustrates the power circuit of the AC-DC stage of the proposed IOC, along with the depiction of four distinct winding configurations.

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Figure 22: Different types of single-phase Integrated on-board chargers; (a) with diode rectifier, (b) active PFC with parallel connection, (c) active PFC with series connection, (d) active PFC with hybrid connection.

Single-Phase IOC with diode bridge

In this type of single-phase IOCs, there is a diode rectifier as the front-end stage rectifying the AC grid voltage. According to the application requirements, there are different structural options:

5.2 Boost PFC (P1)

As shown in Figure 23, by closing relays number ‘1’, motor windings are connected in parallel and T4 operates as the boost converter switch. Resultant equivalent circuit is shown in Figure 2. Current paths in each time interval (T4 ON and OFF) are shown in red and green lines, respectively.

Figure 23: Equivalent circuit of single-phase IOC with diode rectifier.

Operation of the charger in this condition is simple because it works like a boost PFC and conventional dual-loop PI controller shown in Figure 24 can be used to regulate DC voltage and control input current.

Figure 24: Dual-loop PI controller for single-phase IOC.

5.3 Interleaved boost PFC (P2)

In Figure 25, if relays '2' remain closed during the charging mode, the three-phase H-bridge (T1–T6) operates as a three-phase interleaved DC-DC boost converter (Figure 25). In this condition, the converter achieves a voltage gain equivalent to that of a conventional boost PFC. However, the interleaved boost PFC configuration significantly reduces current ripple, which, in turn, helps lower current THD. As depicted in Figure 26, the control scheme becomes slightly more complex due to the need for phase-shifted gate pulses for T2, T4, and T6. Nevertheless, the control structure remains based on a PI controller.

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Figure 25: Schematic of Interleaved boost PFC (P2)

Figure 26: Controller schematic of IOC with interleaved boost PFC

As shown in Figure 26, the control strategy consists of a voltage control loop and a current control loop. The voltage control loop uses a conventional PI controller to regulate the output voltage by adjusting the duty cycle of the DC-DC converter. In the current control loop, a PI resonance controller is employed to track the generated rectified current reference signal. This resonance controller effectively compensates for the harmonics at the grid frequency, allowing it to achieve a high-performance power factor correction (PFC). The result is a near-unity power factor with a sinusoidal input current, meeting grid standards and ensuring efficient energy conversion.

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5.3.1 Simulation results

Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the simulated charger and the JJE motor model, which uses the L-matrix parameters provided in Figure 27. The detailed power circuit is illustrated in Figure 28.

Table 1: Simulation Characteristics

Converter Parameter	Value
$V_{DC,ref}$	680 and 750 V
V_g	220 V (rms)
L_1, L_2	1.5 mH
C_o	3000 μ F
Power	6.6 kW
Switching Frequency	50 kHz
Line Frequency	50 Hz

0.0054	-0.0011	-0.0019	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	-0.0013	-0.0004
-0.0011	0.0054	-0.0018	-0.0013	0.0003	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	-0.0006
-0.0020	-0.0018	0.0063	-0.0004	-0.0007	-0.0001	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	-0.0001
0.0003	-0.0013	-0.0004	0.0054	-0.0011	-0.0019	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0000	0.0003	-0.0006	-0.0011	0.0054	-0.0018	-0.0013	0.0003	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0001	0.0001	-0.0001	-0.0020	-0.0018	0.0063	-0.0005	-0.0007	-0.0001	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0002
0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0003	-0.0013	-0.0005	0.0054	-0.0011	-0.0019	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000
0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	-0.0006	-0.0011	0.0054	-0.0018	-0.0013	0.0003	0.0001
-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	-0.0001	-0.0020	-0.0018	0.0063	-0.0004	-0.0007	-0.0001
0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	-0.0013	-0.0005	0.0054	-0.0011	-0.0019
-0.0013	0.0003	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	-0.0006	-0.0011	0.0054	-0.0018
-0.0004	-0.0007	-0.0001	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	-0.0001	-0.0020	-0.0018	0.0063

Figure 27: JJE L-matrix

Figure 28: Power circuit of the simulated charger

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Figure 29 illustrates the DC voltage (V_{DC}), highlighting the voltage loop controller's ability to accurately track the reference voltage as it transitions from 680 V to 750 V. This demonstrates the controller's responsiveness and stability under dynamic conditions. In addition, Figure 30 presents the grid voltage and current, showing that the charger operates at a unity power factor, with a low-THD input current, reflecting the system's high power quality. Furthermore, Figure 31 depicts the generated inductor current reference alongside its corresponding feedback waveform. This alignment indicates the current loop controller's effectiveness in precisely following the reference current, even during load variations. Finally, torque and speed of the motor are depicted in Figure 32 to show the torque cancellation of the motor.

Figure 29: Output voltage (V_{DC})

Figure 30: Grid voltage and current.

Figure 31: Generated reference and feedback of the inductor current.

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Figure 32: (a) Torque, and (b) speed of the motor.

5.4 No need to have access to star point of windings (P3)

Another converter topology has been proposed in the literature to address the need for access to the winding's star point, as shown in Figure 33 . The operational concept of this topology is similar to that of a two-phase interleaved boost IOC. Current paths in each time interval and controller schematic are shown in Figure 34 and Figure 35, respectively. For further details, please refer to [1]-[2].

Figure 33: Schematic of single-phase IOC with diode rectifier and no need for having access to windings star point

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Figure 34: Switching states of the converter for different modes during charging.

Figure 35: Controller schematic

5.4.1 Simulation Results

Figure 36 depicts the simulated circuit of P3, where only switch T4 is modeled, and T1 is replaced by its anti-parallel diode. To simplify the model and improve its clarity, other switches are omitted. The input voltage is set at 220 V (rms), and the output voltage is 680 V. Additionally, Figure 37 illustrates the motor windings, as previously explained in Figure 33.

As shown in Figure 38, the implemented controller effectively tracks the output voltage reference while maintaining precise control of the input current.

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Figure 36: Simulation model of P3

Figure 37: Motor windings in P3

(a)

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(b)

Figure 38: (a) output voltage, (b) input current and voltage.

Figure 39; Input current THD

5.5 Single-Phase IOC with Active PFC (P4)

Figure 40 illustrates power circuit of single-phase IOC with active PFC with different windings configurations. Table 2 provides an analysis of the operational and structural characteristics of these configurations. The number of reconfiguration switches (RS), which may include mechanical relays, is a crucial factor influencing the efficiency, volume, cost, and reliability of the system. Following this, the number of active switches (AS), which impacts system efficiency and the complexity of the control system, is the next factor under analysis. The winding configuration, coupled with variations in winding manufacturing, results in differences in the amplitude of the winding currents and, consequently, discrepancies in inductance values. These differences can lead to either balanced or unbalanced currents in the windings.

Table 2: Winding Reconfiguraion Methods Comparison

Method	No. of RS	No. of AS	Balanced Currents
Series	4	4	Yes
Parallel	2	4	No
Hybrid	3	4	No

Figure 40: AC-DC stage in charging mode; (a) equivalent circuit, (b)-(c) positive grid half-cycle, (d)-(e) negative grid half-cycle.

As depicted in Figure 40, in charging mode, the AC-DC stage operates similarly in the first three methods (Series, Parallel, Hybrid), resembling an H-bridge rectifier with an equivalent circuit illustrated in Figure 40(a). The current paths of this stage are illustrated in Figure 40(b)-(e), revealing distinct patterns in both positive and negative half-line cycles. Notably, during the positive and negative half-line cycles, T4 and T1 exhibit high-frequency operation, each with a duty cycle D_g . Specifically, the operation during the positive half-line cycle is outlined as follows, and the operation during the negative half-line cycle is briefly described in Figure 40(d)-(e).

Time interval #1 ($0 < t < D_g T_s$): During the initial time interval, switch T_4 is activated and conducts, allowing the inductor to magnetize through the pathway illustrated.

$$\frac{di_{L_{eq}}}{dt} = -\frac{r_{L_{eq}}}{L_{eq}} i_{L_{eq}} + \frac{1}{L_{eq}} v_g$$

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$$\frac{dv_{C_1}}{dt} = -\frac{i_{DC}}{C_1}$$

Time interval #2 ($D_g T_s < t < T_s$): when switch T_4 is deactivated at $t=D_g T_s$ the diodes of T_1 and T_6 start conducting, facilitating the transfer of stored energy from the inductor to the DC capacitor.

$$\frac{di_{L_{eq}}}{dt} = -\frac{r_{L_{eq}}}{L_{eq}} i_{L_{eq}} + \frac{1}{L_{eq}} (v_g - V_{DC})$$

$$\frac{dv_{C_1}}{dt} = \frac{i_{L_{eq}}}{C_1} - \frac{i_{DC}}{C_1}$$

$$\frac{V_{DC}}{v_g} = \frac{1}{1-D_g}$$

The dual-loop PI controller, depicted in Figure 41, is applicable for regulating both the power factor and V_{DC} . Comprehensive analysis, modeling, and control methodologies for the AC-DC stage operating in Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM) are provided in reference.

Figure 41: Control schematic for the AC-DC stage.

5.5.1 Simulation results

The proposed IOC employing series, parallel, or hybrid connections is simulated using MATLAB/Simulink, and the results are presented in this section. The characteristics of the simulated model are detailed in Table 3. The flux density of the simulated permanent magnet motor during charging mode is shown in Figure 42. As the rotor position during the charging process influences the generated torque, the average torque as a function of rotor position is depicted in Figure 43 to analyze its effects. It can be observed that series and parallel connections exhibit lower average torque compared to the hybrid connection. Additionally, Figure 44 and Figure 45 show the generated torque plot and speed of the motor in first rotor position shown in Figure 43 (Elec. Degree=0). As can be seen, although the motor is in standstill condition in all types of connections, series and parallel connection have better performance compared to the hybrid connection.

As discussed in Section III.A, during the charging mode, the currents of the motor phases are unequal in the hybrid connection, as depicted in Figure 46(a). This discrepancy results in unbalanced motor characteristics. As shown in Figure 46(b), the currents of the motor phases are identical in the series connection. Figure 47 illustrates the AC-DC stage performance. The excellent capability of the PFC (utilizing stator windings as filter) in controlling the power factor and providing sinusoidal current is

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demonstrated in Figure 47(a). Additionally, it is evident from Figure 47(b) that its Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) is less than 5%. Output DC voltage is also shown in Figure 47(c).

Table 3: Simulation Characteristics

Converter Parameter	Value	Motor Parameter	Value
V_g, V_{DC}	220 (rms), 500 V	No. of Pole pairs	3
C_1	5000 μ F	No. of Slots	36
Battery Power	5 kW	Output	11 kW
Switching Frequency	5 kHz	Rated Voltage	400 V
Line Frequency	50 Hz	Rated Current	38 A
		Rated Torque	35 Nm

(a)

(b)

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(c)

Figure 42: Flux density of the motor in: (a) Series connection, (b) Parallel connection, (c) Hybrid Connection.

Figure 43: Average value of the torque as a function of rotor position.

Figure 44: Torque of the motor in charging mode.

Figure 45: Speed of the motor in charging mode.

(a)

(b)

Figure 46: Currents of motor phases in: (a) Hybrid connection, (b) Series connection.

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Figure 47: Simulation results of the AC-DC stage in charging mode; (a) Grid voltage and current, (b) FFT analysis of the grid current, (c) DC voltage.

5.5.2 Experimental Results

The proposed single-phase integrated charger with active PFC (P4) is implemented and the prototype is shown in Figure 48. Prototype characteristics are provided in Table 4 and results are shown in Figure 49.

Figure 48: Implemented prototype

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Table 4: Prototype Characteristics

Converter Parameter	Value	Motor Parameter	Value
V_g, V_{DC}	110 (rms), 320 V	No. of Pole pairs	4
C_o	1200 μ F	No. of Slots	18
Power	400 W		
Switching Frequency	20 kHz		
Line Frequency	50 Hz		

V_{in} (30 V/div)

i_m (1 A/div)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 49: (a) input voltage and current, (b) output voltage, (c) generated gate pulse

6 Three-phase integrated on-board charger

6.1 Power Circuit

The components already available in the drive train of EVs are reconfigured to work as an integrated on-board battery charger. The block diagram of the integrated battery charger based on the split three-phase PMSM is shown in Figure 50 where driving inverter of EV is utilized as rectifier and windings of the split three-phase PMSM are used as a grid filter, placed between the grid and the converter. In the split three-phase PMSM, stator windings are split into two equal halves and these windings are arranged in stator at

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an angle of zero degree electrically, which permits the use of the existing three-phase machine design. With these winding arrangements, machine can be viewed with two three-phase stator windings making an angle of zero degree.

Figure 50: Simplified block diagram of integrated on-board battery charger [3].

When the windings of PMSM are reconfigured to be used as a filter, the basic requirement is to keep the rotor of the machine in the rest position without using any external mechanical force. Otherwise, it draws high magnetizing current from the grid and the system will become less efficient. With this condition, connections for the split three-phase PMSM are developed so that the average electromechanical torque generated by the motor is equal to zero. Electromechanical torque in the motor is generated only when there is RMF in the air gap of the motor. This is the key point for developing the connections.

In this approach, RMF is canceled by the connections such that half winding will have the opposite phase sequence of the supply, as shown in Figure 51. Hence, the RMF developed by both winding is opposite to each other, which leads to the cancellation of RMF. The first three-phase winding (R_f Y_f B_f) is having (RY B) supply phase sequence and the other half winding (R_s Y_s B_s) is having (RBY) supply phase sequence, which means that first winding of both three-phase set is supplied by R-phase and supply of second and third winding is interchanged. Therefore, PMF will be developed across R-phase in the motor where it increases and decreases its field along the R-phase axis, as shown in Figure 52. The magnetic field of Figure 52(b) and (c) is half of the magnetic field present in Figure 52(a). It is observed that the presence of PMF in the motor increases the equivalent value of filtering inductance. In induction motors (IM), it makes the parameters unbalanced as PMF interacts with rotor of the IM, EMF is induced in the rotor circuit and current starts to flow. Consequently, the rotor parameters affect the filter parameters and make them unequal. The value of L_{eq} for R-phase is higher than that for the remaining two phases. However, in PMSMs this issue is tackled due to the rotor structure.

For the opposite phase-sequence connection, only one case is considered in which the R-phase is commonly connected between the two windings, as shown in Figure 51. Two more options are possible with the Y-phase and B-phase [3].

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Figure 51: Opposite phase-sequence-based connections. (a) Series. (b) Parallel.

Figure 52: Magnetic field in stator with the opposite phase-sequence-based series connection at (a) $t = 0.005$ s, (b) $t = 0.0133$ s, (c) $t = 0.016$ s, and (d) flux density [3].

Using this method and based on the series connection of the winding parts, proposed charger is designed as shown in Figure 53.

Figure 53: Proposed charger schematic

During the charging mode, as shown in Figure 54, the mechanical relays numbered “1” are closed and other relays are disconnected.

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Figure 54: equivalent circuit during charging mode

- E-Gear Functionality

Traditional methods to extend the operational speed range of PMSMs include field weakening and the incorporation of mechanical gearboxes. Field weakening involves injecting a d-axis current to reduce the flux linkage from the permanent magnets, thereby decreasing the back EMF. While this method is straightforward to implement, it often results in reduced efficiency, torque output, and dynamic performance. Alternatively, mechanical gearboxes can extend the speed range but introduce additional complexity and energy losses. An innovative solution to overcome these challenges is the implementation of an electrical gear, or e-gear, which utilizes reconfiguration switches to alter the winding connections of the motor. This approach enables the transition between series and parallel winding configurations, effectively doubling the efficient speed range of the PMSM without the drawbacks associated with field weakening or mechanical gearboxes. The e-gear concept can be realized using either semiconductor-based switches, such as thyristors and insulated-gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs), or mechanical switches like relays and contactors. Semiconductor switches offer rapid transition times in the microsecond range and have a predicted operational lifespan of several years under typical urban driving conditions. However, they require complex and often bulky bidirectional switching units to handle alternating current (AC), leading to increased costs and conduction losses.

In contrast, mechanical relays provide a simpler and more cost-effective means of reconfiguring winding connections. Although they exhibit longer transition times, typically in the range of tens to hundreds of milliseconds, this duration is comparable to the shift times of advanced mechanical gearboxes in vehicles. Moreover, mechanical relays boast a mechanical lifespan of at least one million operations, aligning well with the operational expectations of passenger vehicles designed for lifespans under 500,000 kilometers.

The proposed charger is equipped with the E-gear enhancing the powertrain performance during driving mode. As shown in Figure 55, windings parts can be connected in series and parallel forms during the driving mode using relays numbered '2' and '3', respectively.

Figure 55: E-gear performance of proposed charger during driving mode; (a) Series connection, (b) Parallel connection.

6.2 Controller

Dual-loop PI controller concept can be used to control the proposed charger to regulate the DC voltage and correct power factor.

The conventional dq current control method can be used due to its simplicity and effectiveness under balanced grid conditions. This approach transforms three-phase AC signals into a synchronous rotating reference frame aligned with the grid voltage vector. By doing so, it simplifies the control of active and reactive power into DC components.

Mathematical Framework

Using the Park transformation, three-phase currents are transformed into the synchronous reference frame (dq-frame):

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\omega t) & \cos\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) & \cos\left(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ \sin(\omega t) & \sin\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) & \sin\left(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix}$$

Here:

i_d : The active current (aligned with the grid voltage vector).

i_q : The reactive current (orthogonal to the grid voltage vector).

Control is achieved using PI controllers, which regulate i_d and i_q :

$$V_d = K_p(i_{d,ref} - i_d) + K_i \int (i_{d,ref} - i_d) dt$$
$$V_q = K_p(i_{q,ref} - i_q) + K_i \int (i_{q,ref} - i_q) dt$$

The outputs (V_d and V_q) are then transformed back to the three-phase domain to generate the necessary control signals for the rectifier switches.

Implemented PI-based controller is shown in Figure 56. First, in the voltage controller, the error between the measured and reference DC voltage are used to generate $i_{d,ref}$ using a PI controller. As we want to work in unity power factor condition, $i_{q,ref}$ is assumed zero. Then, the current controller loop controls the input currents by generating V_d and V_q , which finally transformed to V_{abc} and be used in PWM block.

The implemented PI-based control strategy, illustrated in Figure 56, consists of two main loops: the voltage control loop and the current control loop. In the voltage control loop, the error between the measured DC voltage and the reference DC voltage is processed by a PI controller, which generates the direct-axis reference current, $i_{d,ref}$. To ensure operation under unity power factor conditions, the quadrature-axis reference current, $i_{q,ref}$, is set to zero.

Subsequently, the current control loop regulates the input currents by generating the voltage references V_d and V_q . These control signals are then transformed from the dq-reference frame back to the abc-reference frame to produce the three-phase voltage references, V_{abc} , which are used as inputs to the PWM block. The PWM block drives the switching of the converter, ensuring precise control of the input currents to meet the desired power factor and THD requirements.

This control structure not only achieves tight regulation of the DC bus voltage but also ensures balanced, sinusoidal input currents with low total harmonic distortion (THD), making it suitable for high-performance power factor correction (PFC) applications.

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Figure 56: Dual-loop PI controller for three phase IOC.

Advantages

- 1- Simplified Control: Converts AC variables to DC, enabling straightforward PI controller implementation.
- 2- Decoupled Active and Reactive Power Control: Enables independent regulation of active and reactive components

Limitations

Under unbalanced grid conditions, the *dq* frame encounters significant challenges:

- 1- Oscillations at $2w$: Unbalanced grid voltages introduce negative-sequence components, causing oscillations in i_d and i_q .
- 2- Cross-Coupling Effects: The interaction between positive and negative sequences leads to poor regulation and distorted currents.
- 3- Degraded Performance: The conventional *dq* controller fails to maintain desired performance during unbalanced grid voltage conditions.

The double synchronous reference frame (DSRF) controller extends the conventional *dq* approach by introducing an additional synchronous reference frame aligned with the negative-sequence voltage. This allows for independent control of positive- and negative-sequence components, mitigating the effects of unbalanced grid conditions.

Mathematical Framework

The DSRF transforms three-phase voltages and currents into two sets of dq frames:

1. Positive-Sequence dq Frame ($d^+ \cdot q^+$)
2. Negative- Sequence dq Frame ($d^- \cdot q^-$)

The transformations are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{d^+} \\ i_{q^+} \end{bmatrix} = T(\omega t) \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} i_{d^-} \\ i_{q^-} \end{bmatrix} = T(-\omega t) \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, $T(\omega t)$ represents the Park transformation aligned with the positive-sequence voltage, while $T(-\omega t)$ aligns with the negative-sequence voltage.

Advantages

- 1- Independent Sequence Control: Separates positive- and negative-sequence components, enabling independent regulation.
- 2- Improved Current Quality: Reduces the impact of unbalanced voltages on output currents.

Limitations

- 1- Cross-Coupling Effects: Despite separating the sequences, interactions between positive and negative components remain, causing performance degradation.
- 2- Computational Complexity: Requires two sets of transformations and control loops, increasing computational effort.

Decoupled Double Synchronous Reference Frame (DDSRF) Controller

The Decoupled Double Synchronous Reference Frame (DDSRF) Controller enhances the DSRF approach by introducing a decoupling network to eliminate cross-coupling effects between positive and negative sequences. This ensures superior performance under unbalanced conditions.

The main purpose of DDSRF method is to use a cross-decoupling network like the one, to make the measured current from both reference frames independent from each other. This approach is similar to the one applied for PLLs in synchronization applications

$$\begin{aligned} i_{dq}^{+'} &= \underbrace{i_{dq}^+}_{\text{DC term}} + \underbrace{e^{-J(\theta^+ - \theta^-)} \cdot i_{dq}^-}_{\text{AC term}} - \underbrace{e^{-J(\theta^+ - \theta^-)} \cdot i_{dq}^-}_{\text{Cross-Coupling Term}} \\ i_{dq}^{-'} &= \underbrace{i_{dq}^-}_{\text{DC term}} + \underbrace{e^{-J(\theta^- - \theta^+)} \cdot i_{dq}^+}_{\text{AC term}} - \underbrace{e^{-J(\theta^- - \theta^+)} \cdot i_{dq}^+}_{\text{Cross-Coupling Term}} \end{aligned}$$

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$$i_{dq}^{+'} = \underbrace{i_{dq}^{+'}}_{\text{DC term}} + \underbrace{e^{-j(\theta^+ - \theta^-)} \cdot i_{dq}^{-}}_{\text{AC term}} - \underbrace{e^{-j(\theta^+ - \theta^-)} \cdot (i_{dq}^{-*} - \overline{\Delta i_{dq}^-})}_{\text{DC term}}$$

Cross-Coupling Term

$$i_{dq}^{-'} = \underbrace{i_{dq}^{-'}}_{\text{DC term}} + \underbrace{e^{-j(\theta^- - \theta^+)} \cdot i_{dq}^{+'}}_{\text{AC term}} - \underbrace{e^{-j(\theta^- - \theta^+)} \cdot (i_{dq}^{+*} - \overline{\Delta i_{dq}^+})}_{\text{DC term}}$$

Cross-Coupling Term

The low-pass (LP) filter for obtaining the current error mean value does not need a high selectivity, as it is free from oscillations under steady-state conditions. The cut-off frequency of the LP filter is set to [4]:

$$\omega_f = \frac{\omega}{\sqrt{2}}$$

6.3 Simulation results

The proposed three-phase integrated charger was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink using DDSRF controllers. Figure 58 shows schematic of the simulated model. As shown in Figure 59, the explained torque cancellation method is implemented.

As illustrated in Figure 61, the DDSRF controller shown in Figure 60 successfully tracks the output voltage reference of 950 V. Figure 62 depicts the input current waveforms, where it can be observed that, the DDSRF method demonstrates perfect performance in precisely controlling the input currents.

Figure 58: Simulation model of the proposed three-phase IOC.

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Figure 59: Motor windings configuration

Figure 60: Schematic of implemented controller

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Figure 61: Output voltage

Figure 62: Grid currents.

6.4 Experimental Results

Implemented prototype of the proposed three-phase integrated charger is in Figure 64, and setup characteristics are provided in

Table 5.

1: Converter, 2: Electric motor, 3: dSPACE, 4: Current sensor, 5: Voltage sensor, 6: Load

Figure 63: Implemented prototype

Table 5: Prototype Characteristics

Converter Parameter	Value	Motor Parameter	Value
$3Ph V_g$	110 (rms)	Switching Frequency	20 kHz
V_{DC}	300 V	Line Frequency	50 Hz
C_O	1200 μ F	No. of Pole pairs	4
Power	730 W	No. of Slots	18

Figure 64 illustrates the software developed for the proposed integrated charger, designed for implementation on dSPACE. Feedback from the charger hardware is provided by current and voltage sensors connected via the 'Sensor IO' block. The control signals are generated by the controller block, which employs a Decoupled Double Synchronous Reference Frame (DDSRF) controller. Finally, PWM signals are generated and transmitted to the MOSFETs for operation.

Figure 64: dSPACE software developed for the proposed integrated charger.

Figure 65 illustrates different parts of the controller block shown in Figure 64. Similar to all dual-loop PI controllers, the proposed DDSRF controller has an outer PI voltage controller (blue block in Figure 65) which is a simple PI controller which generates $i_{d,ref}^*$ tracking the DC voltage reference (Figure 66). After that, the inner current controller loop, which shown in Figure 67, is utilized to track the generated $i_{d,ref}^*$. It should be noted that as we want to work in unity power factor condition i_q^+ , i_d^+ , and i_q^- are zero. It is worth noting that the utilized 3Ph PLL shown in Figure 65 is the simple 3Ph PLL block available in MATLAB/SIMULINK library.

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Figure 65: Controller block

Figure 66: PI voltage controller

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Figure 67: Schematic of implemented DDSRF controller

The experimental results obtained using the dSPACE MicroLab platform are presented in Figure 68. Specifically, Figure 68(a) illustrates the three-phase waveforms of the grid, while Figure 68(b) depicts the input current waveforms. As shown in Figure 68(c), the input current remains in phase with the grid voltage, confirming that the charger operates under unity power factor conditions. Additionally, Figure 68(d) highlights the performance of the phase-locked loop (PLL), demonstrating that the detected angular frequency (ωt) accurately tracks the grid voltage. Finally, the output voltage waveform is shown in Figure 68(e), where the controller's performance is evaluated by altering the output voltage reference in four steps (0 V, 300 V, 280 V, and 320 V).

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(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

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(e)

Figure 68: Experimental results. (a) Grid voltage, (b) grid current, (c) voltage and current of phase A, (d) PLL performance, (e) output voltage.

7 Conclusion

The HighScope D3.3 report presents a detailed study of advanced electric vehicle drivetrain technologies, focusing on traction inverters with dynamically reconfigurable windings and integrated on-board charging systems. These innovations aim to improve the efficiency, flexibility, and compactness of EV power electronics while reducing overall system costs.

One of the key advantages of the proposed systems is their ability to extend the operating range of electric machines. The mechanical relay-based e-gear allows for dynamic switching between series and parallel winding configurations, which effectively doubles the motor's speed range from 1000 rpm to 2000 rpm. This flexibility enables better performance across different driving conditions. Furthermore, this switching is achieved with minimal efficiency loss—only 0.09% lower than a conventional setup—and a transition time of less than 35 milliseconds, which is on par with high-end automotive gearboxes.

The semiconductor-based e-gear further improves switching performance by reducing reconfiguration time to less than 10 milliseconds and eliminating torque interruption altogether. This improvement, however, comes at the cost of added system complexity and a noticeable efficiency penalty, with an average efficiency drop of 3.46% due to the conduction losses in the additional semiconductor components and snubber circuitry.

Another strength of the system lies in its integration of on-board chargers (IOCs) using the traction motor and inverter, which reduces the need for dedicated charging hardware. Both single-phase and three-phase IOC configurations are explored, with demonstrated high power quality (near-unity power factor and low total harmonic distortion). The interleaved boost PFC, in particular, showed excellent current ripple reduction and efficient power transfer.

Despite these advantages, the technologies also have notable limitations. The semiconductor-based e-gear is more complex and less efficient than the mechanical relay-based alternative, requiring careful design and additional components. Integrated charger designs also face challenges, such as the need for specific motor winding configurations and potential complications if access to the winding star point is not available.

In conclusion, the HighScope solutions offer promising advances in EV powertrain design. The technologies presented can significantly improve system flexibility and integration but require careful consideration of design trade-offs to achieve optimal results.

7.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

Due to the delayed availability of the traction inverter and its integration with the in-wheel motor, the following actions were taken:

- The validation of the on-board charger was performed using an alternative inverter and an automotive motor with comparable specifications.
- The e-gear strategies were demonstrated on an axial-flux actuator developed in the CliMAFlux project.

For point 2, we want to clearly indicate which activities were carried out in both projects, in line with the GAs:

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- **HighScape:** Conceptual study through simulations of e-gear strategies based on mechanical relays and semiconductor technology for a radial-flux (in-wheel) motor.
- **CliMAFlux:** Adaptation of the developed models from a radial-flux motor to an axial-flux motor within *T3.2. Integrated power electronics for AF motor drives*.
- **CliMAFlux:** Realization of a axial-flux prototype, including reconfiguration switches and the test setup as a part of *T3.2. Integrated power electronics for AF motor drives*. and *T3.2. Integrated power electronics for AF motor drives*
- **HighScape:** Demonstration of the e-gear strategy on an AF actuator design originating from CliMAFlux.

A detailed description of the activities carried out within CliMAFlux can be found in *D3.2: Integration strategy (adopted from EU HighScape) for PE into axial machines* of the CliMAFlux project.

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